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Hybrid Role of Soft Innovation Resources : Finland's Notable Resurgence in the Digital Economy

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ABSTRACT

Finland and Singapore are easy to compare, they are the same size and have similar positions as global digital leaders. however, their performance is differing a lot. from 2006 to 2013, Singapore's GDP growth rate was tenfold compared to Finland. four years later, in 2017 Finland is exceeding the growth rate of Singapore. what are the reasons for the success of Finland? An empirical analysis of the factors contributing to GDP growth and the effects of the policy change was conducted. It was demonstrated that increase of export did not explain growth, but shifts in capital formation did. New dynamics was revealed that was triggered by the removal of structural impediments (hindrances) and by increasing use of soft innovation resources. The virtuous cycle of increase of uncaptured GDP, increased multifactor productivity and growth of tangible capital and GDP was described. An insightful suggestion for activating a hybrid role for soft innovation resources in the digital economy was thus provided.

KEYWORDS

Digital economy, soft innovation resources, multifactor productivity, competitiveness pact, Finland and Singapore

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Exploring Key Elements Required for Organizational Trust and the Consequential Impact on Knowledge Sharing within Organizations

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the status of organizational trust in Muscat and its impact on organizational learning (OL) which is based on the willingness of employees sharing knowledge gathered through experience to improve organizational performance and sustainable competitiveness [1]. Online structured questionnaire and Microsoft Excel used to collect and analyze the data showed significant organizational trust exist within organizations including organizational transparency, management style, employees' welfare and support, and job security. But still, minimal OL and sharing was happening contradicting theories that suggest organizational trust leads to important group collaboration, willingness of employees to share knowledge gathered through their experience and its close link to OL. Lack of compassion and being too controlling at times were also raised as concerns and existing knowledge sharing technological support were also not having much impact. Bringing people together for more effective communications among teams and promoting knowledge sharing culture can lead the way.

KEYWORDS

Organizational trust, Trust Management, Learning and knowledge sharing

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The Impact of Knowledge Management on the Function of Employee Performance Appraisals in Industrial Companies - Case Study

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed at identifying the impact of knowledge management on the function of employee performance appraisals (it is one of the most important functions of human resources management) in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies, relying on the descriptive analytical approach. A questionnaire has been developed and distributed on individuals of the study sample consisting of managers of departments and sections of human resources in each company. The number of questionnaire retrieved and valid for statistical analysis (294) representing (86.5%) of the distributed questionnaires. In order to analyze the study sample, reliance was placed on descriptive statistics, represented in the arithmetic means and standard deviations, in addition to the multiple linear regression analysis in hypothesis testing. The study reached a number of findings, most importantly, the presence of statistically significant impact at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$) for the knowledge management including its dimensions (knowledge generation, knowledge storage, knowledge sharing, knowledge application) on the function of employee performance appraisals in Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies. The study has recommended that the Jordanian industrial public shareholding companies should follow an efficient evaluation system capable of identifying the employees' weaknesses.

KEYWORDS

Human resources management, Knowledge Management, Employee Performance Appraisals, Industrial Companies

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NEO OPEN INNOVATION IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY: HARNESSING SOFT INNOVATION RESOURCES

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ABSTRACT

Successive increases in R&D that creates new functionality are essential for global competitiveness. However, unexpectedly, as a consequence of the two-faced nature of information and communication technology (ICT), excessive R&D results in a marginal productivity decline leading to a decrease in digital value creation. In order to overcome such a dilemma, global ICT firms have been endeavoring to transform themselves into disruptive business model. Neo open innovation that harnesses soft innovation resources may be a solution to this critical question. On the basis of an empirical analysis focusing on forefront endeavors to this dilemma by global ICT firms, this paper attempted to demonstrate the above hypothetical view. Noteworthy findings suggestive to transforming the traditional business model into disruptive innovation that satisfies people's demand corresponding to their shift in preferences in the digital economy is thus provided. In addition, a new concept for R&D resources in the digital economy is postulated.

KEYWORDS

Digital economy, soft innovation resources, neo-open innovation, disruptive business model, transformation

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